

METHODS OF INCREASING THE ACCURACY OF DATA PROCESSING OF AIR TRAFFIC CONTROL SYSTEMS UNDER CONDITIONS OF COMPLEX DISTURBANCES.

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ABSTRACT

This work emphasizes that in complex terrain areas—mountainous and foothill regions—traditional methods of data processing in air traffic control systems often lack sufficient accuracy, which may lead to a decrease in the safety and efficiency of air transport. Therefore, it is proposed to develop methods for improving the accuracy of data processing under conditions of complex noise in mountainous and foothill areas.

A conceptual model of data processing in air traffic control systems adapted to the conditions of mountainous and foothill regions has been developed, taking into account the specific features of multi-component (topographic, atmospheric, radio-technical) disturbances. New results have been obtained regarding the resistance of the developed methods to stochastic and systematic errors, which ensures an improvement in the safety and efficiency of air traffic under complex conditions.

Introduction

Analyzing flight conditions in mountainous and foothill areas is an important task in ensuring air traffic safety, especially during the landing and takeoff phases. The geomorphological features of the terrain, meteorological phenomena, and limitations of radar observation significantly affect the reliability of navigation and the quality of aircraft control. In mountainous and foothill conditions, standard principles of radar support face a number of problems related to signal screening, multipath reflections, and unstable atmospheric conditions.

Theoretical part

In aviation, the impact of interference on radar, navigation, and communication systems is a very important issue, especially in terms of ensuring flight safety, navigation accuracy, and radio communication stability at Termiz, Navoiy, Samarqand, and Namangan airports. These

air traffic hubs serve both domestic and international flights, and their operation depends on the reliable functioning of radio-technical systems.

In radar systems used for air traffic control and landing assistance, radio-electronic interference can reduce the accuracy of aircraft coordinate determination. The main parameter characterizing the effectiveness of a radar system is the target detection probability P_d , which depends on the signal-to-noise ratio.

$$P_d = Q\left(\frac{S}{\sqrt{N}}\right) \quad (2.7)$$

here, S is the useful signal amplitude, N is the noise power, and Q is the Gaussian error function. When the interference power N increases, especially in complex terrain or dense urban conditions that can be observed in the Samarkand airport area, the probability of detection sharply decreases.

In navigation systems, especially satellite-based systems (GNSS), the impact of interference may lead to loss of positioning accuracy or complete signal loss. This is particularly dangerous during landing at airports with limited visibility such as Termiz. Radio-electronic interference can be either unintentional (e.g., industrial noise) or intentional in the form of electronic warfare means. The impact on navigation accuracy can be expressed through the positioning error σ_p , which depends on satellite geometry and noise level.

$$\sigma_p = DOP \cdot \sigma_r \quad (2.8)$$

here, DOP is the Dilution of Precision (geometric weakening coefficient), and σ_r is the standard deviation of pseudorange error dependent on the interference level.

In radio communication systems ensuring communication between the crew and air traffic controllers, interference can lead to loss of information, transmission delays, or distortion of commands. In particular, at high-traffic airports such as Navoiy, the high density of radio transmitters may cause mutual interference. Communication stability is evaluated through the bit error probability P_b , which depends on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

$$P_b = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{N_0}}\right) \quad (2.9)$$

here, E_b is the energy corresponding to one bit, N_0 – noise power spectral density, erfc – complementary error function. $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ when it falls below the threshold value, the probability of error increases exponentially.

Infrastructures at Namangan airport and other regional centers, which may be less protected from external influences, require special consideration of atmospheric and multipath obstructions. The latter occur when signals are reflected from buildings, mountain ranges, or other objects, leading to signal interference and fading. This can be expressed using the Rayleigh model:

$$P_r = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \cos(\omega t + \phi_i) \quad (2.10)$$

here, A_i – amplitude of the wave, ϕ_i – phase shift, ω – angular frequency. In destructive interference, the resulting signal may tend toward zero, which leads to loss of communication.

Discussion

Air traffic services in the airspace of the Republic of Uzbekistan are organized in accordance with international standards and the regulations on the use of the airspace of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and depend on the classification of the airspace in which services are provided [1].

In the absence of continuous radar surveillance and when onboard navigation instruments operate unstably, descent below the lower safe flight level is prohibited. In such cases, the aircraft must proceed to an alternate airport [2].

In recent years, the civil aviation sector of Uzbekistan has achieved significant growth, including the renewal of the aircraft fleet with new airplanes, the introduction of new airport technologies, and an increase in scientific research activities [3–7].

Among foreign studies that have made a significant contribution to the theoretical and practical development of air traffic control, [8] proposes adaptive Kalman filters based on a mixed-state transition model to address the limited accuracy problem in estimating partially navigational states. In integrated navigation based on inertial data, the estimation of the process noise covariance matrix is generalized as a maximum likelihood estimation of variance based on heterogeneous Gaussian mixtures. A sampling method is then proposed to avoid the influence of uncertain sample components on the estimated variance, thereby improving the accuracy of the process noise covariance matrix estimation in integrated inertial navigation systems.

In [9], the scale and duration of interference events recorded from February to December 2022 in the Baltic States, Eastern Europe bordering the Black Sea, and the Eastern Mediterranean region were evaluated using public observation data to determine their impact on civil aviation. The analysis shows various characteristics ranging from isolated events to systematic large-scale and recurring disruptions. Aircraft types involved in relevant flights were identified, and flight plan data were evaluated in relation to navigation equipment to determine flights relying solely on satellite navigation and those requiring backup in case of GNSS loss. Finally, the study demonstrated the impact of GNSS disruption on flight safety.

Modern satellite navigation systems increasingly provide dual-frequency operation capabilities, improving navigation accuracy and reducing residual errors. Recently, the aviation community has begun developing new standardized minimum performance requirements for GNSS equipment to enable future dual-frequency multi-constellation systems (DFMC). In this context, residual errors introduced by GNSS antennas have become more significant, requiring proper characterization and limitation in both antenna specifications and multipath aircraft models. Study [10] addresses this issue by developing new airborne multipath propagation models for L1/E1 and L5/E5a frequency bands, as well as their ionosphere-free combinations.

Experimental equipment described in [11] includes a high-precision radio frequency recording device capable of deep initial correlation analysis of RF spectra around GPS and Galileo carrier frequencies. The results confirm that the observed disruptions are likely caused by artificial radio interference. They also allow in-situ analysis of commercial avionics behavior under GNSS interference conditions.

Millimeter-wave (mmWave) communication systems can utilize wide bandwidth and thus provide very high data transmission rates, for example, several gigabits per second. These systems use directional antennas to ensure optimal distances between communication links. Therefore, directional receiving antennas rotate in azimuth to capture the strongest signal in non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions. In [12], measurement results for 90 GHz systems are presented for three scenarios: indoor, outdoor, and an unusual environment—an airport maintenance hangar.

These issues are particularly relevant in complex terrain regions such as mountainous and foothill areas. In these locations, natural and man-made factors create additional obstacles for navigation and communication. In such conditions, traditional data processing methods in air traffic control systems often fail to provide sufficient accuracy, which may lead to reduced safety and efficiency of air transport operations.

Solving radar support problems in mountainous and foothill regions requires an integrated approach combining engineering, algorithmic, and organizational measures. The main challenges—signal shadowing, multipath reflections, unstable refraction, and limited coverage zones—are being addressed using modern technologies and adaptive strategies.

In [13], a method for detecting and suppressing navigation interference through signal field analysis is presented. The difference between this method and phased antenna arrays is described, where interference cancellation is achieved by subtracting a weighted sum of peripheral antenna signals from the main antenna signal, thus creating distortions in the radiation pattern. Experimental results of interference suppression are provided.

In [14,15], the use of ground augmentation systems at airports, inertial navigation systems, and flight distance-based applications are considered, as well as visual and instrument-based landing aids. Study [16] discusses photometric characteristics of lighting systems. In [17], case studies for wide-body commercial aircraft are used to illustrate and validate the proposed method. In [18], passenger traffic dynamics over a ten-year period at Vilnius, Riga, Tallinn, and Kraków airports are analyzed. Finally, [19] shows that the proposed approach can help airport operators forecast airport load and choose optimal strategies for capacity management in unexpected situations.

Experiment and Analysis

For practical application in Namangan, for example in the design of cellular base stations or radio beacons for navigation, a combination of models is used: empirical (e.g., COST-231 Hata), geometric (ray tracing method), and statistical (Rayleigh or Rice models). This makes it possible to take into account both the macro effects of terrain and the micro-obstacles caused by urban structures.

Mathematical modeling of signal propagation in mountainous and foothill regions requires a complex approach that combines wave physics, terrain geometry, and multipath channel statistics. In the conditions of Namangan, such models are particularly important for ensuring stable communication, accurate navigation, and reliable radar operation, especially in aviation and rescue applications.

For the Namangan region, which has complex terrain and urban development in foothill areas, additional radio signal propagation models that complement classical approaches can be used.

A hybrid model developed based on experimental data in conditions of complex terrain, forested areas, and urban construction combines empirical and analytical components. It allows estimation of electromagnetic radiation levels at different sections of a near-ground radio path. The model accounts for terrain irregularities, including shadowing, reflection, and scattering, and can be adapted to the Namangan region, where alternation of open valleys and dense urban structures is observed.

The Longley-Rice model is designed to calculate radio wave propagation losses in the frequency range from 20 MHz to 20 GHz over distances up to 200 km. It takes into account

digital terrain models, surface type, humidity, as well as diffraction and tropospheric effects. In Namangan, where mountainous obstacles and valleys may be present, the Longley–Rice model allows accurate estimation of coverage and shadow zones, especially for navigation and radar systems.

The Longley–Rice model takes into account the following:

1. digital elevation model (DEM);
2. surface type (soil, vegetation, water);
3. transmitter and receiver antenna heights;
4. climatic conditions (humidity, temperature);
5. signal diffraction, reflection, and tropospheric propagation.

For Namangan, which is located in a foothill zone, the following parameters can be considered: The Namangan aerodrome is situated in a foothill area at an elevation ranging from 400 to 1000 meters. The terrain is uneven, with individual hills capable of blocking radio signals. The land type includes moderately populated areas, vegetation zones, and sparsely distributed buildings.

The frequencies used at the aerodrome are:

- VOR/DME: 116.0 MHz,
- ILS (localizer): 110.1 MHz,
- ILS (glideslope): 334.4 MHz,
- GNSS (GPS, GLONASS): 960–1215 MHz.

For modeling, the VOR/DME frequency of 116.0 MHz is selected.

Antenna parameters:

- VOR/DME antenna height (onboard aircraft): 5 m (on the ground), 1000 m (in flight)
- Distance: up to 150 km

Free-space losses are calculated using the adapted form of equation (2.11) as follows:

$$L_{\text{open area}} = 32.45 + 20 \log_{10}(f) + 20 \log_{10}(d) \quad (2.11^*)$$

here, f is the frequency (MHz), d – distance (km).

for **116.0 MHz** frequency and **150 km** distance:

$$L_{\text{open area}} = 32.45 + 20 \log_{10}(116) + 20 \log_{10}(150) = 32.45 + 41.0 + 20 = 117.25 \text{ dB}$$

for 330 MHz (ILS):

$$L_{\text{open area}} = 32.45 + 20 \log_{10}(330) + 20 \log_{10}(10) = 32.45 + 50.4 + 20 = 102.85 \text{ dB}$$

for 1090 MHz (voice communication station):

$$L_{\text{free}} = 32.45 + 20 \log_{10}(1090) + 20 \log_{10}(10) = 32.45 + 60.75 + 20 = 113.2 \text{ dB}$$

The Longley–Rice model takes into account diffraction, reflection, and shadowing. In mountainous areas, depending on the terrain profile, additional losses of 10 to 40 dB are introduced. For the foothill region of Namangan, the following average corrections can be assumed:

- For 110 MHz: +15 dB (low frequency, better penetration);
- For 330 MHz: +25 dB;
- For 1090 MHz: +35 dB (high frequency, more sensitive to shielding).

Final losses:

- 110 MHz: $L \approx 93.45 + 15 = 108.45 \text{ dB}$;

- 330 MHz: $L \approx 102.85 + 25 = 127.85 \text{ dB}$;
- 1090 MHz: $L \approx 113.2 + 35 = 148.2 \text{ dB}$.

At frequencies below 200 MHz (VOR, ILS), the signal propagates relatively stably in mountainous areas, even with moderate losses. At frequencies above 1000 MHz (radar, GNSS), propagation losses increase significantly, especially in the presence of obstacles.

Based on these parameters, modeling using the Longley–Rice method in the Radio Mobile software produces the following representation (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Radio wave coverage of the Namangan region (Longley–Rice model for VOR/DME)

Modeling radio wave coverage for a 116 MHz VOR/DME system in Namangan region shows the extent of radio coverage in the complex mountainous terrain of the eastern part of the Fergana Valley. The maximum signal strength is observed in the central part of the region—Namangan city—and surrounding relatively flat areas, including parts of the valleys between Chust, Pop, and Kosonsoy. In these areas, the signal propagates along a line-of-sight path, ensuring stable operation of navigation equipment at low and medium flight levels.

However, along the perimeter of the good signal coverage area (green zone), especially in the eastern and southeastern directions, significant shadow zones are formed due to natural obstacles such as foothills and mountain ranges that block VHF signal propagation. The modeling results clearly show shadow zones (red areas) along the borders with Kyrgyzstan and in the southern mountainous slopes. In these zones, natural topographic barriers create so-called “blind” areas. In particular, in regions where the terrain rises sharply in the southwest and southeast, significant signal attenuation is observed.

In the west, in the direction of Kokand and Margilan, the signal coverage gradually weakens with increasing distance from the station. In these areas, especially at low-altitude flight levels, terrain has a strong negative impact on radio coverage, leading to fragmented zones where signal loss may occur.

Thus, the coverage of the 116 MHz VOR/DME system operated at Namangan aerodrome provides reliable navigation in the flat areas of the Fergana Valley, but requires special attention in mountainous regions during route planning. To compensate for “blind” zones, it is advisable to use additional ground stations, repeaters, or integration with satellite-based GNSS systems. For ensuring high-quality radio coverage at these frequencies, increasing antenna height, using relay stations, or employing high-gain directional antennas is necessary.

For the Samarkand region, modeling using the Longley–Rice method in Radio Mobile software produces the following results (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2. Radio wave coverage of the Samarkand region (Longley–Rice model for VOR/DME).

Modeling the coverage of a 115 MHz VOR/DME system at Samarkand aerodrome shows the radio coverage extent for the regions of Bukhara, Navoi, and Jizzakh. The area of strong signal is concentrated in the central part of the region, particularly covering Samarkand city and adjacent relatively flat areas. These zones correspond to areas where aircraft navigation systems can reliably receive signals at low and medium flight levels (shown in green on the map).

However, along the perimeter of this coverage area, especially in the eastern and southeastern directions, significant shadow zones are formed in areas with complex terrain near the foothills of the Zarafshan mountain range. These zones are particularly critical for low-altitude flight operations, as they restrict radio coverage during landing and takeoff, creating so-called “blind” areas.

To the west and northwest, in the direction of Navoi and Bukhara, signal coverage gradually weakens with distance from the transmitter. This attenuation is also influenced by local terrain elevations that create additional obstacles for signal propagation. In these areas, especially near water bodies and forested zones, fragmented signal loss regions may appear due to terrain and vegetation effects that further weaken radio wave propagation.

For the ILS localizer system operated at Samarkand aerodrome, modeling using the Longley–Rice method in Radio Mobile software produces the following results (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3. Radio wave coverage of the Samarkand region (Longley–Rice model for the ILS localizer system)

Modeling the signal coverage of the combined (both runway directions) 330.2 MHz localizer at Samarkand aerodrome demonstrates the directional propagation of the signal along the runway axis. The areas where the signal is received with high quality and minimal losses cover the aerodrome itself and adjacent regions (marked in green on the map), where the signal forms a symmetrical radiation pattern. This ensures precise guidance of aircraft to the runway centerline from both approach directions during landing. These zones include flat areas such as Juma, Nurbuloq, Loyish, and partially Bulungur. In these regions, the terrain has a minimal impact on signal propagation, ensuring reliable operation of the localizer even at low altitudes.

However, along the perimeter of this coverage area, especially in the southern and southeastern directions where the foothills of the Zarafshan mountain range begin, significant shadow zones are formed (marked in red). In these areas, especially during the 271° approach, signal obstruction by terrain elevations leads to a loss of navigation accuracy. In particular, for aircraft approaching from the eastern part of the country, including flights from Tashkent to Samarkand airport, the symmetry of the signal lobe is disturbed in these zones, significantly reducing landing precision.

To the northwest, in the direction of Jomboy and Avazali, signal coverage gradually weakens due to distance and local terrain elevations. In these areas, dense buildings and relief features further increase the likelihood of fragmented signal degradation.

Thus, the coverage of the 115 MHz VOR/DME and 330.2 MHz localizer systems used at Samarkand aerodrome ensures reliable navigation in central and flat areas, but requires terrain considerations in mountainous and peripheral regions during route planning. As noted in the Namangan case, additional measures are required to compensate for “blind” zones.

Conclusion

In general, modern aviation requires not only precise navigation systems but also resistance to radio interference. Modeling, technical auditing, and rapid response to failures are key elements in ensuring flight safety, especially in regions such as Namangan, which have complex terrain and a dense radio frequency environment.

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